

THE THEORY OF COGNITIVE ASPECTS OF THE LINGUISTIC SYSTEM

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Annotation

Taking into account the functioning of language units in the formation of speech based on cognitive content, this article describes the principle of establishing a linguistic system of languages, conducts a comparative study of French and Uzbek language movement verbs from a functional-semantic point of view, and shows the possibilities of a functional-cognitive approach to verbs of action, and the most characteristic similarities and differences related to verbs of this type, as well as universal and based on the identification of idiom ethnic properties.

Key words: Conceptualization, cognitive linguistics, categorization and conceptual.

Аннотация

Данная статья посвящена на функционирования языковых единиц при формировании речи на основе когнитивного содержания, в статье описан принцип становления языковой системы языков, проведено сравнительное исследование движений глаголов французского и узбекского языков с функционально-семантической точки зрения, а также показаны возможности функционально-когнитивного подхода к глаголам действия, а также наиболее характерные сходства и различия, связанные с глаголами данного типа, а также универсальные и идиомотнические характеристики на основе идентификации.

Ключевые слова: Концептуализация, когнитивная лингвистика, категоризация и концептуализация.

Psychologist Dj. The emergence of the science of cognitive linguistics led by Miller and linguist N. Chomsky is currently the biggest event. It is aimed at the study of perception and knowledge cognition in all aspects of its existence. N. Chomsky's unrealized idea that the task of linguistics is to study human cognitive abilities, later his students Dzh. Developed by Lakkoff, R. Langaker, and R. Jackendoff.

The main idea that unites cognitive linguistics into a new direction is that a person's language abilities are a part of his cognitive abilities. The first concepts of the science of cognitive linguistics were the ideas of scientists about the possibility of creating artificial intelligence, as an analogue of human behavior in solving comparable tasks. was to develop the problem of artificial systems of "conscious" behavior, to create information processing programs based on the working principle of the human brain, which is considered as an information system

In its early stages, the cognitive orientation was a reaction to a degree of dissatisfaction with the approach to semantics adopted by the dominant stream of linguistic theory.

If traditional linguistics believes that "language is a sufficiently independent entity that can be studied separately from more general issues of knowledge "algorithmic system", the new direction is based on the idea that "language is a mechanism that does not have an independent meaning. It cannot be explained without the basis of cognitive processes," writes R. Langaker.

Cognitive science includes all disciplines related to the study of the human brain and its work in several directions: the logical direction, which deals with the study of the formal rules of thinking, with the mechanisms and processes underlying the acts of thinking. combined the neurophysiological direction, which focuses on the problem of the interdependence of language and thinking, and the psychological direction based on the study of all forms of mental activity in its real empirical manifestations

The cognitive direction in science traditionally existed in the spheres of philosophy and psychology. Knowledge of the external world, perception, cognition issues have been the subject of research of philosophy since ancient times. Nowadays, cognition is an interdisciplinary science, which is related to operational thinking, the processes of knowing the world, and combines various sciences (philosophy, psychology, linguistics, logic, anthropology, neurophysiology, cybernetics) to interpret certain aspects of a person. Cognitive science, which arose as an interdisciplinary experience of studying the nature, structure, and functioning of the mind, found its continuation in modern linguistics, where it is "the study of knowledge, collected and known in the way people perceive and understand the world. "is the basis of mental or cognitive processes and the results of objective cognitive activity presented in the information system, somehow shown in our mind," describes the famous linguist I.S. Kubryakova.

Nowadays, there is a growing interest of linguists in the problems of organization of learning and its manifestation in language, because the character of language units in speech communication is determined in advance by conveying various knowledge that already exists in lexical and grammatical semantics. Knowledge has long been considered a socio-cultural and psychological phenomenon. At the same time, the role of natural language as the main form of gathering and conveying knowledge about the world was understood. The principles of research focused on the cognitive content and functional function of language units are firmly entering the linguistic habit, because such analysis, which is not limited to formal patterns at the surface level, helps to identify deep semantic processes, in which it is important as a means of communication and communication related to the complex nature of language. hidden laws are revealed. The cognitive approach provides a more adequate definition of material than traditional linguistics, as it is multifaceted and covers all the vast material collected in linguistics.

Cognitive linguistics celebrates the emergence of a new direction in the framework of functionalism, which allows to connect all language processes with the cognitive activity of a person, with acts of categorization and conceptualization of the world. Conceptualization is one of the most important processes of human cognitive activity, it consists of conceptual classification of received information and separation of some minimal units of personal experience in their meaningful form. Conceptualization is inextricably linked with categorization, which is aimed at unifying large classes of language units that show similarity in one way or another or are characterized as exactly the same. provides regulation through. The results of this process are reinforced in the human mind by verbal means, i.e.

lexicalization. The linguistic landscape of the world, on the one hand, is related to the reflection of non-linguistic relations of reality, on the other hand, it embodies the results of the speaker's perception of the world.

The landscape of the world is a holistic, global image of existence, which is the basis of all spiritual activity of a person, all his connections with the world - objective-practical activity, observation, intellectual understanding of the world, and feeling of the world. The landscape of the world consists of a central concept that expresses the uniqueness of the concept of man and his life.

The conceptual landscape has a dynamic character. It is based on conceptual categories that are universal to all languages. The main universals, which are used for real-dynamic visualization of the world, can be included: time, space, life, quantity, movement, state, sign, etc. The listed universal categories form the basis of language categories.

Classifiers, called "scenarios", "frames", "prototypes", "gestalt-structures", which show the direction and forms of knowledge activation in human speech-thinking activity, play a central role in the cognitive paradigm. In this understanding, a lexeme is characterized by the ability to present prototypes and frames to the world, which are part of the structure of knowledge about the world with its meaning - in fact, they are mediators between the content of the language and the expressed reality.

A central concept that reveals ways of expanding knowledge in the content of language units is a frame. The theory of frames was first put into scientific use in the first half of the seventies of the 20th century by the American scientist M. Minsky. The motivation for the beginning of this theory is the fact that a person tries to perceive a situation that is new to him or to look at things that are familiar in a new way, and from his memory he creates some kind of information structure (image) called a frame, in which selects it by changing some details to make it suitable for understanding events or processes. A frame is a data structure for imagining a stereotyped situation. A frame can be thought of as a grid of nodes and connections between them. According to M. Minsky, the "higher stages" of the frame are clearly defined, because they are formed from such concepts, which are always correct in relation to the situation in question. At much lower levels, there were many individual terminals or "cells" that had to be filled with characteristic examples or information. Frame as a complex category of consciousness is a universal category that unites various layers of human knowledge, all his spiritual and practical experience.

A frame is a set of associations stored in memory. The frame assumes a complex situation; it can be compared to a "frame" that includes all that is typical and important for this set of conditions. A frame is a possible model, that is, a person, if he has knowledge of reality expressed in words, if he knows the sequence of events that awaits him within a concrete situation. , perceives one or another language structure. The frame can be considered as the embodiment of human social experience, it is a "holographic appearance" in the collective consciousness of the speaking subjects. The frame, like concepts, is characterized by a diverse functional-meaningful volume. A microframe contains knowledge about concrete, rare situations; A macroframe provides comprehensive information about the ways in which a macroconcept can be expanded, including all of their forms and modifications, that unites different types of events in a broad sense. According to M. Minsky, the frame theory was developed to explain the speed of human perception and thinking, as well as to explain the absence of observable mental phenomena accompanying this process.

Frames implement different ways of visualizing the knowledge that is brought to life in the process of human speech thinking.

The derivative "schema" of thinking is close to the concept of "landscape of thinking". The concept of "schema" means a series of symbols with the help of which the cognitive system is represented, the structure of the "external" world is perceived and processed in the "internal" world of the human mind. At the level of the scheme "the tree in general" - the trunk and branches from it; it is possible to fully imagine "shoes in general" - a scheme that repeats the shape of a human foot, and so on. A schema emerges as an abstraction from details to enable categorization and subsequent thought and action based on the categorization. Schemes are conceptual structures, with the help of which a perceptual and cognitive picture of the world, separated by lexical means, is formed in a certain way. The concept-scheme actualizes space schemes and quantity schemes

Scenarios are distinguished from frames by a decisive factor of time measurement, which is frames in dynamics. A script, unlike a frame, consists of a complete package of information and contains detailed symbolic knowledge. A script consists of several acts or episodes, each of which is divided into more convenient units, the meanings of which, in turn, depend on cultural and social factors. R. Schenk, L. Birnbaum, and Dj. According to Mayler's proposed definitions, "a well-developed script is essentially a chain of pre-arranged, simple sequence of events. By using a script, the understanding subject can link together ideas that are unrelated to his external aspects: he does this by relying on a previously connected memory structure. The following Uzbek phraseology can be cited as an example of the scenario: play hide-and-seek, squint, work, don't stop, burn my face).

Pictures, schemes, frames and scripts of thinking, which are "understood" by lexicographical descriptions, are included in the structure of knowledge visualization. Mental phenomena such as "insight" - "getting into the essence" can be added to them. These are symbols that give information about the structure, design and functional purpose of the object: scissors (a cutting instrument consisting of two blades joined by screws between two circular handles), umbrella (a device for protection from rain or sun: a long a circular piece of cloth drawn on a folding spoke attached to a pen).

In addition to these, the structure of ideas about knowledge also includes concepts of figurative, spatial components, devoid of any emotional components of perception; they are decoded with purely logical definitions: honor, reputation, glory (spiritual and moral principles of a person worthy of respect and pride; good, untarnished name, pure name), conscience (a sense of moral responsibility for one's character in front of the surrounding people, society), etc.

Insights can be characterized as the most primitive denotations, their structure is known to everyone from early childhood and does not need a detailed explanation at all. Insight-building schemas convey information about the object's structure, design, and functional intent

Cognitive linguistics makes it possible to connect all language processes with human cognitive activity, categorization and conceptualization of the world. Conceptualization is one of the most important processes of human cognitive activity and consists of conceptual classification of the information that comes to him. It is aimed at separating some minimum units of human experience in an ideal meaningful form. The process of conceptualization is inextricably linked with categorization, which is aimed at uniting rather large classes of units

that show similarity in one way or another, or are characterized as exactly the same. If the structural-structural approach answers the question of the structure of the object, the functional approach allows to answer the question of what is the function of this object.

Functional description studies language not from "form to content", but from "content to form", "from function to language tools". This principle of describing language material is completely legitimate, because it reflects the path of thought that arises in the mind of the speaker - from the concept to the means of its expression. In the process of forming an opinion, the speaker always moves from the idea he wants to express to the formal means used to express certain information.

The cognitive task is related to how the phenomena of the external world are reflected in the language through human perception and thinking, that is, this task requires the accumulation of the subject's knowledge and social experience. Giving his knowledge to another, the individual separates himself from the other individual and from the world, which explains the communicative origin of thinking.

The cognitive task implements the multifaceted relationship of language, thinking and objective being, which until now was interpreted as the connection of word content and concept. At the same time, the current level of linguistic knowledge provides an opportunity to conceptualize the connection between language and thinking, to assess the generalization of human mental experience. To solve this problem, it is necessary to take into account that the language expresses some elements of the external world, as well as complex human knowledge related to events, situations, episodes. In recent years, various models that generalize the forms of relations of language to knowledge and experience have been put forward, based on the laws. Among them, for example, the model of cognitive processing of knowledge put forward by U. Cheif can be mentioned. He defined the process of conceptualization of previous experience, which includes separation of episode, propositionality, and categorization.

Cognition reflects the process of perception of reality, and the reflection of reality is based on the formation of a conceptual picture of the world, which predetermines the linguistic picture of the world and focuses on the lexical system. Ye.S. Kubryakova says that the connection between the linguistic landscape of the world and the conceptual landscape is made through words.

Speech-thinking activity implies the presence of a set of knowledge about the surrounding world in the speaker, which a person acquires in the process of cognition. Knowledge is the development of imaginations, concepts, ideas, which is a social condition. Cognitive activity of people is directed to the objects of the surrounding world and is directly connected with practical activity. Knowledge is stored in the human mind in the form of coherent thematic groups related to different areas of life experience.

Cognition is understood as the property of language to summarize the events and features of the external world learned by a person, so that the cognitive task contributes to the creation of an individual's knowledge fund. Eat. According to S. Kubryakova, "language shows the presence of various structures of knowledge about the world in our heads, which is based on such a unit of mental information - a concept. Concepts of various forms (images, imaginations, concepts) or their combinations (pictures, gestalts, schemes, diagrams, propositions, frames, etc.) arise in the process of perceiving the world, they are formed in the

processes of cognition, human experience and the variety of activities with the world.
-reflects and summarizes reality (truth) understood in its various forms.

Cognitive science is the science of knowledge perception and information processing systems. It is based on the study of general principles that govern thought processes. The product of the thinking process is knowledge. Knowledge is "the result of knowledge of reality tested in socio-historical experience and confirmed by logic, its adequate reflection in the human mind in the form of ideas, concepts, opinions, theories. Language is a component of human thinking activity and comes as the main means of expressing thoughts and reflects knowledge, so learning a language is an indirect way of learning knowledge.

Cognition makes it possible to present the lexical system of the language in a new perspective, explaining it differently through the prism of the perception of human thinking. The content of the vocabulary, which reflects the processes of organizing knowledge in the head of a person, related to the processing and storage of knowledge, the conceptualization of the experience of language speakers, enters the internal lexicon of a person (Gafarova, Kildibekova 1998, 40).

Cognitivism allows for a new interpretation of the content of language categories, their hierarchical structure, because it implies the systematization of all types of knowledge based on human cognitive activity. From a cognitive point of view, language units are considered to be a reflection of certain layers of human experience recorded in language. In this regard, during the analysis, it is necessary to determine what structure of knowledge each of the categories records, what role it plays in the reduction and expansion of knowledge, to describe and implement the specific intention (intention) of the participants of the speech act at different levels.

The cognitive approach allows a new look at the issue of interdependence between the lexical system of the language and grammar as the two main links of the language, because the universal conceptual categories are defined in the lexical contents as the main concepts at the level of the dictionary and at the level of grammar.

The cognitive approach can be used in the analysis of linguistic phenomena both in the grammatical and lexical fields. Based on cognition, word groups, separate classes of words, for example, verbs, word-forming processes, functional-semantic categories are analyzed, etc. For example, the category of temporality, which is characterized by a multi-layered structure, is based on the cognitive activity of a person to place events in the center of time. The perception of the movement of time is directly connected with events and situations.

Time is not observed and is recorded in the human mind through events, and performs the task of event-distribution in language. The speaker moves the sequence of events from a certain counting point of his choice to the timeline. Cognitive models of temporality cover various aspects of human experience, including a wide spectrum of time relations.

The cognitive approach allows for a new interpretation of the general categorical meaning of word groups. For example, it is impossible to study quality as a sign of words without referring to different areas of thoughts, the principles of understanding the world in the process of knowing it. Usually, adjectives are considered to name special features and characteristics of objects. But there are many adjectives in the language, whose meaning is determined by describing the whole situation and events.

The most important task of cognitive semantics is to describe the types or methods of transition from one meaning to another; this is done on the basis of different language and different lexical, word formation, grammatical meanings material.

The most important thing for cognitivism is to look at language, first of all, as a link between speech and thinking, on the one hand, and as a cognitive mechanism, on the other hand, on the part of language functioning.

It is difficult to overestimate the importance of the cognitive approach in studying the lexical system of the language. Thanks to the cognitive approach, it was possible to imagine the semantics of language units in a completely different way, which consists in systematizing the vocabulary of the language based on global concepts. Within such a large-scale scientific paradigm, cognitive linguistics, a separate department - cognitive semantics - is distinguished, which deals with the issues of understanding and using language, and differs from ordinary semantics in terms of setting problems and methods of solving them. The problem of the relationship between language and knowledge accumulated by humanity brings the issue of cognitive semantics to the first echelon of research that allows a new understanding of the traditional topics of linguistics as a means of language learning and the problems of the relationship between language and thought.

Cognitive semantics aims at the conceptual analysis of language, which includes the study of various mental structures, as well as the various ways in which these structures are represented in the human mind. From the point of view of cognitive semantics, the analysis of lexical units is carried out using the basic categories of concept realization. Conceptualization is one of the most important characteristics of human cognitive activity. Supporters of cognitive semantics Dj. Lakoff, R.Langaker, Dj.Djakendof, L.Talmi and others evaluate the content as an informational structure mentally encoded in natural languages, and the process of reflection of reality in the human mind as occurring through various types of schematization.

Cognitive science studied mental processes and the results of these processes - knowledge. According to Ye.S. Kubryakova, cognitive science tried to connect with various fundamental and new, developing sciences: information theory, computer science, neuroscience. Cognitology combines several sciences at the same time, i.e. it is not only an interdisciplinary science, but a science under the "umbrella" of science, the purpose of which is to study the processes connected with knowledge and information in one way or another; it is a science that combines different disciplines to interpret certain aspects of human thinking.

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